

Deliverable 6.2

Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Work Package: WP6 Dissemination & Exploitation

Grant Agreement Number: 101094766

Due date of deliverable: 30/04/2023

Actual submission date: 30/04/2023

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Due date of resubmitted deliverable: 15/12/2024

Actual date of resubmission: 15/12/2024

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Dissemination Level: public (PU)

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Co-funded by
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UK Research
and Innovation

Deliverable Information

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Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	<p>This document provides detail of the instruments, tools and processes to be deployed by the Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation (GREAT) project partners and associates to engage stakeholders, raise awareness and leverage the project outcomes, outputs, findings and results. In conjunction with the supporting, associated, dynamic 'activity plan' the document will be used by the project to inform, manage and operationalise dissemination and exploitation activities. The core elements of the plan are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To provide an integrated and consistent external profile for the project, to facilitate recognition, raise awareness and engage identified target groups. • To ensure visibility of the project's actions, activities, outcomes, research findings, and events. • To disseminate extensively and intensively the achievements of the project and the effectiveness of the GREAT approach to targeted audiences. • To leverage the international networks that are linked to consortium members. • To provide a roadmap for successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes. <p>This first version of the deliverable (D6.2) will be updated and revised with a second iteration at a later point of the project in month 30. The updated version (D6.4) will incorporate specific details of activities undertaken, strategic updates and reflections informed by the emergent experience of the project as it progresses.</p>
Keywords	Dissemination, Exploitation, Feedback
Statement of originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

Document History

Version	Date	Comment (Examples)
0.1	04.07.2023	Draft 0.1 document created
0.2	10.04.23	Main content added to all sections
0.3	14.04.23	Peer review and detailed feedback on overall structure and specific content
0.4	21.04.23	Integration of peer review comments and final editing
1.0	29.04.23	Document complete and submitted
1.1	29.11.24	Exploitation Plan added to the deliverable, improvements made, sent out to reviewers
1.2	13.12.24	Reviewers' comments integrated and completed

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the GREAT project consortium under EC grant agreement number 101094766 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	Editorial Board
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

The EU Horizon Europe GREAT project (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation) presents an opportunity to provide new insight and understanding of digital games' cultural and social potential. It will achieve this by undertaking research inquiries to provide and pilot innovative solutions that harness the agency and scale of gaming audiences to generate valuable insight into society and create a step-by-step change in citizens' participation in public debate. Moreover, it offers unprecedented opportunities to exploit the scale, speed, agility, and diversity of inquiry in data collection. The project will engage with three core aspects: games, data and policy in a single programme of research and innovation with the ambition of applying games to create a new form of engagement and dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders (policy-makers, policy implementers, political parties, campaigning organisations and affected citizens). In doing so, the project aims to demonstrate that digital games can positively impact social engagement by harnessing the innovative potential of a game space within which citizens are willing to express their preferences and attitudes.

The purpose of this deliverable, in conjunction with the D6.5 Sustainability Strategy, is to provide strategic direction to raise awareness of the project and its intended outputs, engage key stakeholders, gather input, and promote the exploitation and sustainability of the intended outputs. The document will contribute to the longevity of the project outputs, discussing scalability and repeatability through a playbook toolkit accessible from the project website. The project will engage positively with industry to ensure a rich project legacy of outputs, outcomes and methodologies. The focus of the WP6 is to *"reach and engage stakeholder groups to input expertise and perspectives into the project, share findings, outputs and recommendations and inspire maximum uptake from stakeholder groups, and beyond."* and the core elements of this deliverable within it are to:

- Provide an integrated and consistent external profile for the project to facilitate recognition, raise awareness and engage identified target groups.
- Ensure the project's actions, activities, outcomes, research findings, and events are visible.
- Extensively and intensively disseminate the project's achievements and the GREAT approach's effectiveness to targeted audiences.
- Leverage the international networks that are linked to consortium members.
- Provide a roadmap for successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes.

The primary audience for this deliverable is internal, the Executive Management Board (EMB) of the GREAT project to inform the EMB of the rationale behind the recommendations to deploy appropriate tools and instruments to engage stakeholders. This deliverable and, specifically, the associated activity plan will enable the partners

of the project to identify, manage and undertake dedicated dissemination activities consistent with the project aims and objectives. The associated activity plan will function as a dynamic repository of dissemination and exploitation activities for the duration of the project.

2. Introduction

The GREAT project is committed to maximizing its impact by actively disseminating and exploiting its findings. Since February 2023, we have engaged with diverse stakeholders, including policy-makers, games companies, and the general public, through targeted activities guided by evidence-based, data-driven processes. This commitment extends to collaboration with associated Horizon Europe innovation projects and initiatives. This document outlines our comprehensive approach to *communication, dissemination, and exploitation*, ensuring the project's methodology, data, and technology are leveraged effectively. This second iteration of Deliverable D6.4 reflects valuable insights gained from stakeholder engagement throughout the project and provides clear guidance for leveraging project outcomes. The following presents three Key Focus Areas:

1. **Communication:** Informing the general public about the project and its outputs through various channels, including press releases and social media. We leverage the reach of existing games to connect with a diverse audience, ensuring balanced representation across gender, age, education level, and location. For example, Play2Act has a global and diverse demographic reach, demonstrating our ability to engage with a wide range of individuals from different countries, social, economic and educational background, age etc. This is explained in detail in section 3.
2. **Dissemination:** Sharing results with specific target groups using tailored messaging and audience segmentation strategies. This approach (detailed in Table 1 and explained in detail in section 4) ensures strong connections and effective knowledge transfer. Activities include:
 - Presenting at international conferences, workshops, and webinars.
 - Publishing in academic journals, scholarly texts, and industry periodicals.
 - Depositing academic outputs in the Zenodo EU repository.
 - Producing white papers and guidance documents for policy stakeholders.

3. **Exploitation:** Putting the project's results into practice. This includes:
 - Developing a user-friendly GREAT toolkit with practical guides for applying the project's methodology.
 - Providing long-term access to anonymized data on Climate Policy Radar.
 - Maintaining a project website (<https://www.greatproject.gg> with regular blog posts and updates).

This multifaceted approach ensures that the GREAT project's valuable contributions reach a broad audience and are effectively utilized to address critical societal challenges. This is explained in detail in section 5.

3. Communication Strategy and Plan

Communication is how we inform the general public of the project, and this can be through press releases, media and other more general ways to reach a wider audience. This is important because citizens play a massive role in the overall project and are key stakeholders, as the methodology and data should directly benefit global citizens. As part of the communications strategy, the project can reach vast and diverse audiences through existing games. Games have a variety of audiences depending on the genre, platform and type of model (free vs premium), which is all tracked in the data and enables the project team to keep a close eye on diversity of the audience and results.

The goal or mission of the internal communications strategy is to have a clear plan for partners to follow, to communicate and disseminate information, either to the broader public or specific stakeholder groups. The process will enable PlanetPlay to be the central source to manage communications but give each partner the flexibility to raise awareness of the activities that may be specific to them. Although PlanetPlay leads this WP, each partner is responsible for contributing to the work package. Various documents, from blogs to scientific papers, are created to raise awareness and engage stakeholders through dissemination to exploit the results in various ways. Each project partner will create and communicate different outputs, attend events, or make a discovery. For each of these items, each partner is responsible for following the workflow below:

1. **ALL:** In the bi-weekly meeting, each partner will discuss dissemination they have been involved in (see list of actions and items in KPI document for reference).
2. **ALL:** If there is nothing to report, please state this. Partners will be expected to contribute to dissemination at least every 8 weeks, ideally monthly.

3. **ALL:** Create a short blog about the dissemination activity (event attended, speaking slot, paper, discovery, etc.) with text visuals and bullet points to summarise the activity or the action, and send it to PlanetPlay to be uploaded onto the project website.
4. **PP:** Post the blog onto the website first, then post the blog on LinkedIn (to drive more traffic to the website overall) with hashtags #greatprojectgg and other associated hashtags such as #play2act (hashtags will enable a quick search and filter to review engagement results).
5. **PP:** Share posts by email to ALL partners, and ALL partners are expected to share on their LinkedIn profiles for their organisations and individually (collective reach of 500k followers across profiles on LinkedIn).
6. **ALL:** On a monthly basis, PlanetPlay will review the collective data and add it to a tracker to keep track of engagement metrics.

PlanetPlay will generate a suite of assets which can be edited by each partner, such as social post templates, academic posters, etc.

4. Dissemination Strategy, Plan and KPIs

There are multiple target groups identified through audience segmentation (the first iteration of our segmentation strategy is provided in Table 1) that the project will actively engage with during the duration of the project. Our audience segmentation strategy will be refined as the project evolves. At the centre of the project, dissemination will be the dynamic activity document. This will be subject to ongoing review by the project team to regulate and monitor the efficacy of all communication and dissemination activities to ensure that the project strategy is refined and remodelled logically and incrementally to reflect stakeholder engagement input.

4.1 Methodology

The dissemination process objectives are to stimulate the interest and attention of the identified audiences and target groups. The messaging and ways in which we communicate through a range of channels will be dynamically reviewed as we deliver messaging to understand the efficacy of our communication approaches and strategy as well as the mechanisms and channels selected, which will be refined and adjusted by ongoing audience feedback. The dissemination process/cycle is detailed in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Dissemination Methodology.

4.2 Target Groups

To engage with stakeholders, we have identified various audiences and the communication methods, tools and instruments by which to engage them.

Table 1: Audience Segmentation (Target Groups and Comms Channels).

Target Groups	Primary Messages	Communications Tool, Instruments and Channels
Citizens and game players	GREAT provides new ways for you to provide input and effect to policy-makers and implementers, in a simple, convenient way.	Embedded activities in games giving broad reach to a variety of demographics across gender, age and education level. Press releases, blog posts on the website, social media.
Academia (games researchers, social scientists, technologists)	GREAT research provides new insights and evidence of the efficacy of digital games and their potential role in society.	Research publications, conferences, bibliographic listings on the GREAT website, journals, periodicals and books (consortium partners have published a number of books/journal articles/papers on relevant topics with major publishing houses).
a) Games publishers and providers b) Games developers	a) GREAT reveals new opportunities for new applications of games, with guidance, resources, demonstrators and business models. b) GREAT provides a method and resources to implement games. leveraging game data for social purposes.	Blog posts on the GREAT website. Industry conferences (e.g. Games for Change, GDC, Gamescom, Pocketgamer, SXSW). Social media. Networking by partners. Targeted contributions to industry websites (e.g. ISFE, EDPF) and leading bloggers. For data analytics: SOLAR, LACE network.

a) Policy-makers b) Policy implementers c) Environmental policy stakeholders	a) The GREAT method offers new ways to consult with citizens who do not participate in the traditional media and democratic process, and to assess their preferences and attitudes (reaching the hard to reach) b) The GREAT method is a new way to obtain feedback on results of policy implementation c) GREAT insight reports can help you in formulating and responding to policy on the climate crisis	Networking by partners (e.g. with UNESCO, UNECE, House of Lords UK) and policy events (Institute of Government and Public Policy, User Centred Policy Design, (Apolitical), social media. Press releases and newsletters. Participation in climate crisis conferences (Davos, UNGA, COP, PlanetTech, Websummit, TedX, and UN, events run by UNEP, UNFCCC and UNDP). Hosting roundtables at the EU Commissions buildings in Brussels bringing together policy-makers and games studios, policy-makers attending events / roundtables at gaming events i.e. Nordic Game 2025.
Political parties, campaigning organisations	The GREAT method creates opportunities for widening participation in your activities.	Press releases, targeted distribution of newsletters and insight reports. Social media

The segmentation is not intended to be a prescriptive approach as with any iterative, agile project evolves; we expect that the segmentation and associated methods, tools and instruments will evolve, and new groups emerge as informed by our continuous stakeholder engagement.

4.3 Editorial Board

All project partners will contribute to content development and participate in dissemination activities. However, an Editorial Board (EB), the WP leaders, has been established to manage, advise, regulate and monitor the quality, relevance and adequacy of content and messages being communicated as directed and informed by this plan. The GREAT editorial Board will initially consist of the following members as representatives of the contributing partners to the project:

- DIPF Jane Yau
- ZSI Claudia Fabian
- PM Jude Ower
- UNIR Joaquin Alonso
- UoB Rebecca Harris
- SGI Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen
- FU Anna Merry

It is envisaged that regular meetings of the EB will take place to collate, review and approve content and materials informed by the dynamic activity plan. The board's purpose is to ensure that the project will maintain a dynamically rich and multichannel flow of information, material and content from the expertise and perspectives of the partner organisations. It is anticipated that the ongoing dissemination of content and materials will be incorporated into the exploitation plan to be provided within the next iteration of this document in Deliverable D6.4.

Figure 2: EB Approval Structure.

4.4 Deliverables and Milestones

Table 2 shows the related deliverables concerned with the dissemination and exploitation of the GREAT project.

Table 2: Dissemination and Exploitation Deliverables within WP6.

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Type	Due Date	Comments
D6.1	Website	Website	07.2023	The website will host project and partner information, updates, white papers and social media links. Access to games and data will be linked too.
D6.2	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	Report	04.2023	The report will be deposited on Zenodo .
D6.5	Sustainability Strategy	Report	01.2026	The report will be deposited on Zenodo .

Table 2 Dissemination and Exploitation Deliverables within WP 6

4.5 Channels, Tools and Instruments

To facilitate effective communication with segmented audiences and maintain ongoing dialogue engagement with the project, the following channels tools and instruments are deployed by the project:

- **Website:** The GREAT website will contain project information, partner information, and updated, dynamic information, including live data and materials, papers, games and tool kits. A guide has been developed for social and website posts.
- **Mailing list:** The Project will establish a mailing list on the website to include email registration subject to GDPR requirements.
- **Newsletter:** The EB will coordinate the updating of the website and develop a project e-newsletter to be distributed periodically during the duration of the project as required.
- **Social media:** Social media accounts will be established on Twitter, Bluesky, and LinkedIn, which are believed to be the most beneficial for the project. These will be updated regularly during the project and coordinated by the EB.
- **Assets:** Assets for social posts and logos, including project and funders' logos, will be used.
- **Reports:** Partner reports and papers will be produced by all partners and coordinated by the EB. These will be from a variety of perspectives on emergent topics within GREAT.
- **Proactive public relations (PR):** PR activities will also help to drive awareness and new followers/collaborators, and each partner will be asked to undertake PR activities as required. A relations pack will be produced, which will also be available on the website and can be shared by all project groups/partners (ALL).
- **In-game activations:** In-game activations will also drive awareness of the project and engagement from the player community (engaged over one million gamers/citizens to date).
- **Scientific Committee:** The project established a Scientific Committee (located in WP4), responsible for the custodianship of all academic activities. This responsibility includes all academic dissemination. The Scientific Committee exercises oversight of ethics and quality control procedures in compliance with EU and UKRI requirements for the project's duration.

4.6 Activities

The consortium will undertake various activities to raise awareness of and engage with the project's key target audiences to build relationships with relevant individuals and organisations. As highlighted earlier in this section, the dynamic activity plan is the repository and location of all dissemination and engagement activities and events, as well as details of the project partners who are responsible (see Table 3).

Table 3: A sample of the Dissemination Activity Plan.

Starting	Ending	Channel	Target Audience	Dissemination	Activity Name	Outco	link (URL or	status	Objectives	Lead
1/2/23	30/4/23	Other	All	Other	Logo			Delivered	To have a visual to represent the project and be added to materials etc	PM
1/2/23	15/5/23	Website	All	Other	Website landing page			Delivered	An initial page to raise awareness of the project and project partners, until main site is launched	PM
1/2/23	30/06/23	Website	All	Other	Website			Ongoing	A central resource to contain information about the project, partners, updates, papers, PR and links to games and data	PM
23/3/23	23/3/23	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	speak at Sustainable Innovation 2023		https://cfsd.org.uk/events/sustainable-innovation-2023/programme/	Delivered	To raise awareness of the project with industry at a sustainable online conference	UoB
6/23	6/23	Event	Innovators	Conferences	Speaking at Irish Games Based Learning Conference (Cork)		http://www.iqbl-conference.com/	Delivered	To attend and speak at conference to raise awareness and meet partners	UoB
17/7/23	25/7/23	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Games for Change Festival		https://festival.gamesforchange.org/	Delivered	Exposure across industry and non-profits	PM
20/7/23	30/7/23	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	SDG Summit at the UN/Raising profile via a book launch and ongoing book promotion			Delivered	To raise awareness of the project via a book on the topic of games being a force for good	PM
23/8/23	27/8/23	Event	Industry, busine	Meetings	Gamescom Cologne			Delivered	To meet with key industry stakeholders at the major European games event, Gamescom	PP

The activities to be included but are not limited to in the dynamic activity plan:

1. Conferences

The project will take part in targeted conferences, such as:

- i. Speaking opportunities i.e., the UN SDG & Gaming Summit
- ii. Hosting panels and roundtables
- iii. Hosting workshops or masterclasses
- iv. Distributing papers and data

2. Associated Events

When there are opportunities to engage with fringe events and activities, such as:

- i. Side presentations
- ii. Socials
- iii. Workshops/roundtables both virtual and physical representation

3. **Focus Groups**

GREAT will engage with focus groups online and offline to investigate specific topics or challenges. This activity may be undertaken alongside the project activities in citizen science located in WP5 of the GREAT project.

4. **Associated Existing Groups/Activities**

GREAT will engage with established and associated groups, activities and initiatives that may relate to the project, such as:

- i. Online forums and networks, including 'Playing for the Planet',
- ii. GGJ, United Kingdom Interactive Entertainment (UKIE)
- iii. Sustainability Group, International Game Developers Association (IGDA)
- iv. Games Developers Association Special Interest Group (GDA/SIG), COP, UNDP People's Climate Vote (other climate and policy events).

5. **Engagement with associated EU-Funded Horizon Europe Projects**

The project will engage with our associated sister projects commencing with a virtual meeting with the projects in May 2023 with the objective of introducing our project to consider which synergies and clustering activities would benefit our respective projects specifically in respect of the future dissemination of the results and the potential for collective preparation of policy recommendations. The five sister projects are:

- i. **EPIC-WE** (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments)
- ii. **LoGaCulture** (Locative games for cultural heritage)
- iii. **i-Game** (Building a community for the co-creation of games with high impact on innovation, sustainability, social cohesion, and growth)
- iv. **MEMENTOES** (Immersive games for museums as vehicles to engage visitors in empathetic responses)
- v. **MuseIT** (Multi-sensory, User-centred, Shared cultural experiences through interactive technologies)

4.7 Dissemination Instruments and Tools

4.7.1 The Project Logo

The GREAT project has its own distinct logo, which will be used on all materials, including the website, publications, presentations, blog and social media posts. The logo is a vibrant visual that sums up gaming and is used in conjunction with a simple font of GREAT.

Figure 3: The logo for the GREAT EU project.

4.7.2 Funders Logos

Consistent with the grant agreement alongside the GREAT logo, the EU Horizon Europe logo and UKRI logo will be applied across all materials, as demonstrated in the footer of this document; this will be the standard document template for all deliverables. The material will also contain, as required, the project Grant Agreement Number and accompanying text.

"This [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] is part of the project / joint action '101094766 / GREAT', which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (2023 - 2026)"

When displayed in association with another logo, the EU emblem will have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries will use the EU emblem and accompanying caveat note.

"The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, etc.] represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility; it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency or any other body of the European Union. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains."

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Figure 4: Logos of the funding agencies of the GREAT project.

4.7.3 Presentations

The project team will be required to attend events and present materials. In this context, presentation decks will also be used to generate material not reports or whitepapers. A template has been created for the project team. The Great Project Presentation Template document is also presented below:

Figure 4: GREAT Project Presentation Template.

4.7.4 Website

The website (<https://www.greatproject.gg>) is a key tool for dissemination, communication and exploitation. It will be a central hub which will host and/or link to various information and materials to raise awareness and provide detailed information of the project and the progress and results as the project develops. We will present the following:

- 1) Project overview and partners
- 2) Games (The DiBL - Dilemma Based Learning Games)
- 3) Reports, white papers and other publications
- 4) Data dashboard (link to GitHub or other such repository)

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- 5) Methodology details
- 6) Social media links
- 7) PR and media (with approval for usage on the site or link to the site)
- 8) Project Playbook and Toolkit (when available)
- 9) Link to Zenodo
- 10) Policy documents

This list is not exhaustive, and throughout the project, we will accommodate other materials and outputs that emerge to present to stakeholders or the result of stakeholder consultation.

Figure 5: Website Landing Page.

Key dates for the website development are:

- 15th May - Landing page live.
- 30th June - Website launched.

The editorial board (EB) will meet periodically to discuss website content and agree materials and information as this is incorporated. Each member of the EB will have access to the website Content Management System to upload information and material. Quality control will be managed by the EB on an ongoing basis.

4.7.5 Hashtags

For all posts on social channels, mainly LinkedIn and X, the following hashtags will be used to enable the WP leader to track engagement data on posts and mentions:

- The main project hashtag = #greatprojectgg
- Case Studies can also be tagged, such as = #play2act

4.8 Progress on KPIs for Dissemination

There are several key performance indicators (KPI) for dissemination activities incorporated into the Grant Agreement document, and these provide quantitative targets for the project. The EB will work across all work packages to achieve these KPIs. Table 5 highlights the KPIs set out at the start of the project with an updated view of progress along with strategies for those KPIs, which are more ambitious.

Table 4: Planned Activity KPIs of the GREAT project from DoA.

General Public (communication)	Games Industry (dissemination)	Policy Stakeholders (dissemination)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website (100,000 unique visitors) • Player communications (3 million contacts) • Open participation in games (300,000 players) • Participation in design of games and data analysis (100 per cycle) • Press releases (at least each 6 months) • Social media (at least monthly to Twitter) • Research publications (at least 20) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conference presentations (20, at least 5 at industry events or trade fairs) • Academic publications in games journals (5) • Social media (monthly to LinkedIn & Discord) • Participation in EC events (3, if suitable) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings with key stakeholders (25 formal meetings) • Insight briefings for policy makers (5) • Toolkit for games companies (1, updated) • GREAT described in magazine and external website articles (at least 6)

Table 4: Planned Activity KPIs of the GREAT project from the DoA

The GREAT project has demonstrated considerable strengths by achieving and surpassing key performance indicators (KPIs) in many areas by M20, highlighting its impact and progress (see Table 5). Notable achievements include exceeding engagement and reaching goals, such as engaging 760,000 players (target: 300,000), reaching 130 million players (target: 3 million), and achieving global participation from 190 countries (target: 8). Collaborative efforts have also been highly successful, with 30 game studio partners and extensive involvement from policy bodies. Dissemination and stakeholder engagement remain strong, with 26 external presentations (target: 20), 9 industry presentations (target: 5), and very positive feedback from stakeholders, particularly in workshops and industry roundtables.

Future Actions for Remaining KPIs

1. **Publications and Case Studies:** Progressing toward the target of 20 publications (currently 11) and five case study reports (currently 1) remains a priority to ensure the scientific and practical insights of the project are well-documented and shared.
2. **Policy Briefings:** Expanding the number of policy insight briefings and promoting their visibility on climate-related platforms will further enhance the project's policy impact.
3. **Games and Data Collection:** Delivering 12 fully designed games and methodologies for policy-relevant data collection, as planned, will solidify the project's unique contribution to the field.
4. **Whitepapers:** Completing whitepapers on games in democracy education and policy stakeholder applications will provide impactful resources for long-term dissemination.
5. **Website and Social Media:** Continued refinement of the communication strategy to focus on engagement metrics (likes, shares, and comments) over raw follower counts will ensure meaningful stakeholder interaction. Ongoing updates to dashboards and collaborations with industry publications will drive further visibility and engagement.
6. **Policy Adoption and Business Models:** Increasing the number of policy bodies adopting GREAT methods (currently 8, target: 30) and promoting business model downloads (currently 148, target: 1,000) will enhance the project's long-term utility.

With a strong foundation already in place, the GREAT project is well-positioned to meet and exceed its remaining KPIs, driving impactful dissemination and stakeholder engagement while ensuring the scalability and sustainability of its outcomes.

Table 5: Updated progress of KPIs in December 2024.

ID	Target by M36	Reached by M20
1.	20 Publications	(On track) 11 Publications published
2.	5 Policy Insight Briefings (300 downloads)	(On track) 1 completed (125 downloads), Policy insight for Green Roofs & for Green Jobs, Climate Week - Industry evaluation
3.	5 Case Study Reports	(On track) 1 published
4.	Project Video (600 views)	(On track) <u>Video produced (157 views, 372 Impressions on LinkedIn)</u>
5.	500 participants in co-design & activities	(Completed) 140 in Test Cycle & 200 in Green Jobs & 115 in Green Roofs
6.	300,000 players engaged	(Exceeded) 760,000 players engaged
7.	3 million players reached	(Exceeded) 130 million players reached across 20 games titles and platforms including Xbox, Unity and Amazon Games
8.	Engagement of diverse participants in > 8 countries	(Exceeded) 190 countries covered
9.	Collaborative engagement with 25 rep. from games companies & policy bodies	(Exceeded) Currently 30 game studio partners, 3 games platforms and 7 policy bodies
10.	5 Industry Presentations	(Completed) 9 incl. Web Summit, participating in Nordic Game in May 25
11.	20 presentations at external conferences/events	(Exceeded) 26 presentations at external conferences/events
12.	50 mentions of Policy Insight Briefings in external climate websites	(In progress) Once we have more policy insight briefings, UNDP Play2Act will gain broader public interest & followers.
13.	Stakeholders in workshops give positive evaluation	(Completed) very positive feedback from industry, policy-makers, gamers (NYC Climate Week roundtable with SYBO games)
14.	12 games to gather data which is valuable for policy stakeholders.	(On track) On DiBL approach, we will delivering at least six fully designed games. With the PP approach we will provide six examples of how its survey technology can be used within existing games to gather valuable data from players. As stated in <u>D3.1</u> , in total, we will cover 12 games that demonstrate in different ways how to gather valuable data for policy-makers. These different methodologies will be documented and analysed in the case studies. The collected data will be made available for open access (as defined in section 4 of <u>D3.1</u>).
15.	30 Policy Bodies taking steps to adopt GREAT methods	(On track) Currently 8, Austrian Climate Agency, Cyprus Energy Agency, Urban Gorillas, Waterwise, UNDP, House of Lords (UK), New Automotive, Dept of Environment in SA,
16.	Games industry give positive feedback	(Completed) Very positive feedback on value, input on business model and roundtables (April and Sept 2024)
17.	1000 downloads of Business Models	(On track) Currently 148, released on 31.7.2024
18.	A page of relevant work by other researchers	(Completed) <u>Zenodo community (Zenodo) & Zotero Group (Zotero)</u>
19.	Create a LinkedIn group	(Completed)

20.	5 Press releases (every 6 months)	(On track) currently 4 (Kick-off, Earth Week 24, UNDP Play2Act 24, Web Summit 24), PR from FU
21.	6 magazines / websites refer to GREAT	(On track) 7 in the Global Young Academy (<u>Connections Magazine, 2023, 2024</u>), <u>Falling Walls, UNDP, Mirage News, Devdiscourse, Digital Frontiers</u>
22.	10,000 followers across all GREAT social media activities	(In progress) The project has made significant progress in leveraging social media, with a collective following of 541,000 on LinkedIn and 85,000 on X, alongside active sharing on platforms like Instagram, Facebook, X, and LinkedIn, including posts from game studios encouraging public participation. Recognizing the limitations of follower counts for long-term impact, the project has shifted its focus to tracking engagement metrics such as likes, shares, and comments across social media platforms of the whole consortium instead only on the newly established GREAT accounts. This approach ensures more meaningful and sustained interaction with stakeholders, fostering deeper connections and active participation in the project's communication and dissemination activities. Moving forward, the project will enhance its strategy through targeted content, dynamic posts, and leveraging partner networks, aligning its social media impact with broader engagement and dissemination goals.
23.	1000 downloads / views of Newsletter	(In progress) Currently counting 1100 website visitors. UNDP Play2Act press release and other materials will gain a wider public interest & viewers, collaborations with major industry publications.
24.	A whitepaper on the use of games democracy education	(To be done) potential collaboration with industry publications to gain wider traction, partnership with Newzoo in Q1 2025 which will reach the games industry and beyond.
26.	A whitepaper for policy stakeholders	(In progress) DRAFT version created from roundtable hosted with SYBO games and UNDP at the NYC Climate Summit in September 2024.
27.	100,000 unique visitors to the website and other GREAT information products	(Exceeded) The original KPI of 100,000 unique visitors to the GREAT project website has proven to be a narrow measure of the project's extensive multi-media outreach dynamics. With the rise of large-scale case studies in the fall of 2024, such as Play2Act, the project has adopted an updated communication strategy that better reflects the broader and more impactful scope of its dissemination efforts. This updated approach focuses on two key aspects. First, website visibility is being enhanced by linking back to the project website through blog posts shared across various social media channels. While this drives traffic to the website, the primary goal is to foster deeper engagement with the project through posts, public relations efforts, and stakeholder interaction. Second, and more significantly, the project leverages large-scale case studies like UNDP Play2Act to provide public real-time information dashboards, which serve as a software-as-a-service dissemination and exploitation tool for both the gaming community and policy-makers. These dashboards have had an unprecedented impact, far exceeding the original outreach goals. For instance, the PlanetPlay GREAT x UNDP Play2Act dashboard has already recorded over 125,000 views, with 35,000 gamers expressing interest in taking actionable steps on climate change challenges. Similarly, the forthcoming UNDP dashboard is expected to amplify these metrics further. These real-time, interactive tools provide visibility and engagement that extend beyond the GREAT website, making them a highly promising avenue for achieving the project's dissemination KPIs and amplifying its impact.

4.9 Political and Policy Dissemination Strategy

Dissemination to policy-makers is an integral part of the project to raise awareness of activities and engage this group in the process and, eventually, the outcomes. The GREAT project is mindful of the necessity within the project to engage directly with political and policy-makers. The project will determine these actions by consultation with stakeholders and with the engagement of our project advisor, located within one of the UK partners, Baroness Worthington. The engagement strategy will be detailed in D6.4. It is envisaged that activities will include:

1. Meetings with experts and key influencers - to gain knowledge, insight, and guidance; and as ambassadors, to be able to promote the project and make relevant connections.
2. Host roundtables on and offline with policy-makers and those involved with policy data, such as at NYC Climate Week, and bring policy-makers to gaming events, such as Nordic Game, to undertake deeper discussions and produce policy papers. GREAT is planning to attend the Games Policy Summit, which will take place during Nordic Game 2025 with our sister projects. The plan is to bring together European stakeholders to examine policy measures to boost the growth of the games industry based on culture, innovation, and trade.
3. Host meetings and events in conjunction with policy-makers, such as at the EU Commission's offices in Brussels, and attract key game stakeholders. This is currently under exploration at the EU in June 2025 for World Environment Day.
4. Work with existing groups we know have political agendas, such as Playing for the Planet, UKIE, Project Everyone, Drawdown, UNDP, COP, etc.
5. Create white papers and determine the profile of papers required in the policy space to create impact and knowledge transfer to the policy domain.
6. Create specific policy papers for this stakeholder group to inform them of the importance of gaming in policy-making.

5. Exploitation Strategy, Plan and KERs

This section presents the first version of the Exploitation Plan for the GREAT project outputs. It also contains a first assessment of the potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and the ways and methods the consortium will use to enhance impact and sustainability. The Exploitation Plan has been reviewed and will be updated throughout the project lifespan to foster smooth and successful exploitation of the project results. Another version (D6.4) is due in month 30, where the project's first results will have fed the strategy, early users will have been identified, and the project results will

already be more consistent. Therefore, this plan defines a long-term strategy until the end of the project to pursue the following objectives:

1. Explore and assess application areas to facilitate the exploitation of the GREAT project results.
2. Set the foundations for further opportunities to ensure the achievement of impact during and beyond project end.

The strategies of communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, although they are all discussed in this document, should however not be mixed up. While these strategies share many similarities, it is essential to emphasize their differences. Figure 7 has been obtained from "[Horizon Europe Quick guide and tools for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation](#)" guide, and clarifies the differences.

Figure 6: Taken from Communication, dissemination and exploitation.

The exploitation strategy aims to target three main audiences:

1. Consortium members, regardless of whether they are commercial companies, academic institutions or associated partners.
2. European Commission services and independent reviewers.
3. External organizations (industry, academia, society) and projects, especially those with an interest in GREAT results, further explained in section 5.4.

The exploitation strategy and the continuous process involved will feed into the input of the following GREAT project deliverables:

- D1.2 – Research data management plan: Research data management plan for the project including personal data protection measures. It will affect the creation of datasets.
- D4.4 – Compilation of GREAT scientific outputs: A public document detailing the scientific outputs, including conferences, journals and other publications produced by the partners throughout the project. It will have an impact on the exploitation of research findings.
- D5.3 – Final Impact Assessment Report: Final evaluation and impact assessment based on the evidence collected during the project.
- D5.4 – Policy insight briefs: Targeted policy briefs on game-based society - policy engagement based on the learnings from the project.
- D6.3 – Business models: this deliverable examines the business models applied in using games to link citizens in dialogue with policy-makers examining policy dilemmas related to the climate change crisis.
- D6.4 – Revised dissemination and exploitation plan: Revised dissemination and exploitation plan, with toolkit and resources.
- D6.5 – Sustainability strategy: Sustainability strategy for the post-project phase.

5.1 Common understanding: Terminologies

To understand the GREAT exploitation approach, it is necessary to understand what exploitation is, specifically to define the significance of the results and to highlight the different terminological distinctions. Here, we also include some definitions of dissemination and communication to highlight their differences with exploitation.

- **Results:** “any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected.”
- **Dissemination:** “public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means, including scientific publications in any medium.”
- **Communication:** “strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communication about 1) the action, and 2) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”
- **Exploitation:** “use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities”. According to the definition, exploitation refers to the use of the

results of the project. The definition does not address purely commercial needs. It opens the scope of the application of results to different levels and to different domains to encompass commercial, societal, political and academic exploitation.

- **Commercial exploitation** is concerned with taking the GREAT results to the market, whereas **non-commercial exploitation** is concerned with effectively using knowledge, models, methodologies and standards.
- **Open Source**: “any program where the source code is made available for use or modification as users or other developers see fit”.
- **Open Access**: “Online access to research outputs provided free to the end-user”.
- **Open Science**: “An approach to the scientific process based on open, cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge”.
- **Target audience**: “It is a group of people to whom messages are addressed”.
- **Stakeholders**: can be defined as “people, groups or organisations having an active role because of their interest in the project's activities, e.g., European Commission, Funding Agencies and others”.
- **Networks**: “list of contacts that, even if they do not have an active role in the project activities, can contribute to the wide communication and dissemination of activities. Networks can be of different types”. They can be political, administrative, and union networks, for instance, linked to opinion leaders, media, and scientific networks.
- **End-users**: “A group of persons benefiting from activities’ results”.

5.2 Exploitation and its impact relating to GREAT’s objectives

This section presents the exploitation strategy specific to the GREAT project, its objectives, and the expected impact it aims to have, followed by the identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs). These KERs will be analysed, and their unique value proposition will be identified along with the domains and outcomes produced by the KERs. The relevant target audiences are also identified. The formalisation of roadmap planning activities and the definition of clear messages by objectives and target groups are presented.

The GREAT project aims to find a new form of engagement and dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders through games. In doing this, the project will demonstrate that games can positively impact social engagement by exploring the innovative potential of a game space within which citizens are willing to express their preferences and attitudes. Four overarching objectives (as stated in the GA) are shown below:

1. **Objective 1.** Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy-makers. In other words, to produce new knowledge on the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU to benefit society.
2. **Objective 2.** Understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences. In other words, provide evidence of the impact of games on European society by carrying out case studies which focus on how games impact on citizens' participation in European society
3. **Objective 3.** Provide practical guidance for games developers and policy stakeholders. In other words. To generate proposals for improving games in terms of positive impact on education, skillsets, responsible business models, employment chances, social cohesion and creativity.
4. **Objective 4.** Assess the benefits and risks to individuals and society of using games to promote engagement with societal challenges. In other words, to provide evidence of the impact of games on European society, including their cultural value and risks.

As explained in the GA, the project does not only focus on providing academic evidence, but **to achieve a real impact on the selected target user groups, including commercial organizations and policy stakeholders.** Hence, the expected impact is:

New knowledge

- **Impact 1.** As a result of the implemented case studies, the project will generate knowledge on the role of games contributing to society, and the methods that can be applied by the games industry to achieve this.
- **Impact 2.** The project will generate evidence of the innovative potential of games and play, with practical applications in real cases. It will also create a knowledge pool, based on the data obtained from planned case studies, which will be made available to society for academic, commercial and social use.

New opportunities for society

- **Impact 3.** It will also demonstrate how games can be used to create new types of interaction and discourse on urgent social issues, new insights into social dilemmas, and new models of citizen participation in governance.
- **Impact 4.** It will enhance citizens' ability to participate in policy discussions. The increase in participation in policy discussions will have a consequent positive impact on social cohesion, proportional to the success of the project impact

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strategy. On the contrary, it will allow politicians to have direct access to citizens' concerns, thus contributing to decision-making on environmental issues.

- **Impact 5.** It will enhance citizens' awareness about the climate change crisis while contributing to achieving the Green Deal and the UN Sustainable Development goals.
- **Impact 6.** The project will promote new forms of cultural expression. The Game industry is profoundly creative, and it's a terrific tool to foster intercultural cooperation while engaging citizens of any age.

New challenges for the Games Industry

- **Impact 7.** It will open and create a window for the video games industry to engage with and better understand the needs of citizens and the implementation of sustainable policies that affect them.
- **Impact 8.** It will contribute to creating new and innovative business models applicable not only to the video game industry but also to other public sector stakeholders.
- **Impact 9.** GREAT project will increase the games industry's potential to collect valuable data for new and socially beneficial purposes, including new analytics tools and ethical data management methodologies. This will also open, in this sense, a new and sustainable economic activity for game developers and providers.

New capabilities for the consortium

- **Impact 10.** It will also create a network of game studios, intermediaries, legislators, non-profit associations, universities and other institutions aware of using games as a priority communication channel with the public to feed into decision making. This network will assume a global status through collaboration with associated partners, with a presence in four continents.

The overall GREAT project Unique Value Proposition could be described as the opportunity to take advantage of the innovative potential of games and play to enhance new types of interaction and discourse on urgent social issues, collect new insights into social dilemmas, and promote new models of citizen participation in governance. All five identified GREAT Key Exploitable Results have their unique value proposition and are presented in section 5.5.

5.3 Adherence to Intellectual Property Rights

Effective exploitation of the KERs depends on, amongst other issues, the proper management of intellectual property, which should be part of the overall knowledge

management in the project. GREAT project Partners will assess the possibility or necessity of protecting their results once these are generated. In due course, they will choose an appropriate form of intellectual property protection. Standard forms of protection which will be considered include patents, trademarks, industrial designs, copyrights, trade secrets, and confidentiality agreements. In the GREAT project, the following actions will be carried out to address issues related to intellectual property rights, these include:

- potentially protecting the pre-existing knowledge (background) of the project partners,
- an assessment of the results generated during the project,
- proposals for the optimal protection of IPR, and
- ownership and proper implementation of IPR protection measures.

The framework of the IPR management is set out within the Consortium Agreement, which stipulates the rules related to the following IP issues:

- Identification of the background and the specific limitations and conditions for its implementation.
- Ownership of the results.
- Access rights to the background and the results.
- Non-disclosure of the information.

The GREAT project partners have considered it good practice to consult before deciding whether to protect new results, in particular, if the results are a joint outcome.

5.4 KERs for Exploitation

The exploitation of the KERs will focus on how to maximise their impact and value. This process will consist of the following:

1. **Identification:** The project team will identify the most promising results with potential applications or benefits beyond the project.
2. **Assessment:** The identified KERs will be assessed for their market potential, societal relevance, and alignment with industry needs or academic interests.
3. **Protection:** Intellectual property protection mechanisms such as patents, copyrights, or licenses could be applied to safeguard the KERs and ensure their ownership. We will define this in the project at later stages, depending on the requirements of project partners.
4. **Knowledge Transfer:** In the scientific context, exploitation may involve sharing research findings through publications, conferences, and collaborations, thereby contributing to advancing knowledge within the field.

5. **Dissemination:** Disseminating information about the KERs through targeted online activities and events to attract potential stakeholders or collaborators.
6. **Collaboration:** Collaborative efforts with relevant stakeholders, such as partners, research institutions, or policy-makers, to ensure the effective utilization of the KERs.

By defining clear objectives, target audiences, tools, activities, and methods, the exploitation plan ensures the project's outcomes are not just made accessible to scientists, researchers, authorities, and policy-makers but to encourage long-term use of results after the project has ended. The coordination of exploitation activities aims to achieve maximum outreach and impact.

Dimensions of Exploitation

The GREAT project consortium will focus on four dimensions of exploitation. Those dimensions are strongly linked to the expected results and the selected targeted groups. These dimensions are *commercial, societal, political, academic, and research exploration*. These dimensions have been identified for the different target groups to find interest in the partnership activities, allowing the creation or adaptation of specific messages to their communication habits.

5.4.1 Commercial Exploitation

1. *Project Partner Organisations* (PlanetPlay and SGI):
 - Directly integrate the GREAT project's technology into their existing products and services.
 - License the technology to other companies in the gaming industry.
 - Use the data and insights to inform games studios, platforms, and other industries that are interested in the data.
 - Offer consultancy services to other organizations looking to implement similar solutions.
2. *Industry Groups* (Employers' associations, Unions):
 - Utilise the project's findings to advocate for sustainable working practices.
 - Develop industry standards and best practices based on the project's research.
 - Use data to inform negotiations and collective bargaining agreements.
3. *Project stakeholders* (e.g., Games Studios and Developers):
 - Improve green game design and development processes based on the project's methodology.
 - Increase player engagement and retention through data-driven insights.

- Access and leverage the project's platform for user research and feedback.

4. *Platform Holders* (e.g., Unity, Xbox, Meta):

- Integrate the GREAT project's technology into their platforms to enhance user experience.
- Collaborate on research and development initiatives to further advance the technology.
- Use the project's findings to inform platform policies and guidelines.

5.4.2 Societal Exploitation

1. *Sectors of Interest* (e.g. NGOs, lobbying and other organisations):

- Civil Society: NGOs and charities can use the project's platform and data to raise awareness of social issues, promote positive behaviour change, and engage with their target audiences.
- Lobbying organizations (e.g., Think Tanks): Utilize data and research findings to support their advocacy efforts and influence policy decisions.
- Other organizations (International, Multilateral): Organizations like the UN or WHO could use the platform to address global challenges, promote sustainable development goals, and facilitate international cooperation.

2. Exploiting Data for Climate Change:

- Analyse in-game behaviour to understand players' attitudes towards climate change.
- Develop games and simulations to educate the public about climate change and its impacts.
- Use the platform to promote eco-friendly practices and encourage sustainable behaviour.

5.4.3 Political Exploitation

1. *Political Parties*:

- Engage with voters and understand public opinion on key issues through in-game surveys and data analysis.
- Use the platform to test different campaign messages and strategies.
- Run targeted campaigns within games to reach specific demographics and hard to reach audiences.

2. *Campaigning organizations*:

- Mobilise supporters and raise awareness for their cause.
- Gather data on public opinion to inform campaign strategies and push policies.
- Use the platform to connect with potential partners and volunteers.

3. *Legislative bodies* (e.g., MoP):
 - Gather evidence and data to inform policy debates and decision-making.
 - Use the platform to consult with the public on proposed legislation.
 - Simulate the impact of different policies on society.
4. *Governments* (national, regional, local):
 - Improve public services and communication through the platform.
 - Use data to understand citizen needs and preferences.
 - Engage with citizens on policy issues and gather feedback.
5. *EU institutions*:
 - Promote European values and initiatives through the platform.
 - Facilitate cross-border collaboration and knowledge sharing.
 - Use data to inform EU policies and programs.

5.4.4 Academic and Research Exploitation

1. *Academic Partners*:
 - Conduct further research based on the project's methodology and data.
 - Create papers and articles based on the project's outputs and build on existing research and knowledge.
 - Develop new teaching materials and courses using the project's findings.
 - Collaborate on future research projects in related fields.
2. *Associated Projects* (e.g., *EU Games Cluster*):
 - Share knowledge and best practices with other projects in the gaming industry.
 - Leverage the project's results to strengthen the European game development sector.
3. *Research Networks*:
 - Disseminate the project's findings to a wider research community.
 - Foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among researchers.
4. *Researchers (PhD candidates)*:
 - Use the project's data and methodology for their research projects.
 - Contribute to the development and refinement of the technology.
 - Publish research papers and present findings at academic conferences.

5.5 Progress KERs

In a collaborative exercise, in which all project partners were interviewed individually and jointly, the project team collected all the expected results for the project to date. This is the first approximation that will be updated during the course of the project, and this collection of exploitation results will be reflected in deliverable D6.4. The

following table shows the result outputs, their description and the target audience they address, based on the four dimensions identified in section 5.4.

Table 6: A collection of expected results of the GREAT project.

Output	Result Description	Dimension			
		Commercial	Societal	Political	Academic
Business models	Business models applicable in the domain of the use of games to link citizens in dialogue with policy makers examining policy dilemmas related to the climate change crisis, incorporating different value proposition. To help other companies to enhance its services.	✓		✓	✓
Business Models Ecosystem	A report and associated documentation detailing the GREAT business Model Ecosystem	✓		✓	✓
Whitepapers	A whitepaper on the use of games as a medium for education for democracy and development of skillsets in social engagement and participation. A whitepaper for policy stakeholders on the use of games to obtain policy insight.		✓	✓	✓
Policy Briefings	short insight documents from the project that are specifically targeted towards policy stakeholders to advise how the GREAT methodology can be useful for citizen - policy engagement			✓	
Data sets	The CSV files (or equivalent) of the data collected during the case studies	✓			✓
Online data sprint methodology	A suite of analytics methods for game activities	✓			✓
Corpus of case study documentation	The collected documentation of all of the research activities carried out in each case study (planning and reporting documents, working documents, transcripts, etc.)			✓	✓
Academic Papers (journals and conference proceedings)	Publications aimed at collecting the findings of the research activities carried out in the project. Journals, Conference proceedings...				✓
Other scientific outputs	Other results derived from the research activities carried out in the project. PhD candidates, Conference presentations, Posters				✓

Table 7: A collection of expected results of the GREAT project.

Network of stakeholder, including game industry, policy-makers, researchers	New connections for stakeholders involved in GREAT that may lead to further collaborations beyond GREAT	✓	✓	✓
Open Learning Resource	The Green Jobs and Green Roofs DiBL games as open learning resources		✓	✓
GREAT method instruments and documentation	Planning and reporting templates, guidance, data procedures (?),	✓	✓	
Games-based survey method	A games-based method and/or process for conducting large-scale surveys of citizens views on policy dilemmas	✓	✓	
Games-based focus group method	A games-based method and/or process for conducting focus groups		✓	✓
Activity designs	A set of activities for use in the design of inquiries into citizens views on policy dilemmas, specifically (but not exclusively) games-based surveys and focus groups.		✓	✓
DiBL 2.0	An adapted and extended version of DiBL that addresses the feedback from researchers, partners, end-users and policy-makers across the GREAT project. It may include new templates, formats, open access, data freely accessible	✓	✓	
PlanetPlay services 'shared value' data - games	To access millions of gamers for no cost, have an agreement with games studios to provide access to their players in return for data and insights. Surveys, CTA,	✓	✓	

For example, the business models, business models ecosystem outputs, and network of stakeholders (including the game industry, policy-makers, and researchers) can potentially be exploited in the commercial, political and academic dimensions. In contrast, whitepapers and open learning resources can be exploited in the societal, political and academic dimensions. Policy briefs can be exploited in the political dimension. DiBL 2.0 and PlanetPlay services 'shared value' data – games can be commercially and politically exploited. From the list of 17 GREAT exploitable results, as shown in Table 6 and 7, we identified five results that are expected to deliver the most significant and most meaningful impact of the GREAT project in relation to its overarching objectives, as detailed in section 5.2. These are shown in Table 6 below and further explained in the sub-sections 5.5.1, 5.5.2, 5.5.3, 5.5.4, and 5.5.5.

Note that a Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified interesting result which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an essential input to policy, further research or education. The GREAT consortium has identified 5 results that fulfil the prerequisites as mentioned earlier based on their degree of innovation, exploitability and impact.

Table 8: Dimension addressed by GREAT project's Key Exploitable Results.

Key Exploitable Result	Dimension			
	Commercial	Societal	Political	Academic
Methodology for Games industry	✓			
Methodology for policymakers & organisations		✓	✓	
Datasets	✓			✓
Knowledge corpus		✓		✓
DIBL 2.0		✓	✓	✓

(1) The methodology for the Game industry, (2) Methodology for policy-makers & organisations, (3) Datasets (further details provided in 5.5.3), and (4) Knowledge corpus **will be made publicly available on Zenodo**, whereas (5) DiBL 2.0 will not be made open source.

5.5.1 KER1: Methodology for the Games Industry

Description

A games-based method and process for

- 1) facilitating large-scale surveys to be carried out to collect gamer'/citizens' views, and 2) collection of in-depth insights, on policy dilemmas e.g., relating to sustainability or green games/communities.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Using the methodology and tools made available by the project, companies in the sector will be able to open a new way of communicating with customers (via games), provide new services (surveys, information) and offer new products on the market, improving their productivity.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Business Models, Know-How, Games-based survey method, Activity designs, Templates, Surveys, networks.

5.5.2 KER2: Methodology for Policy-makers & Organisations

Description

A games-based method and process for

- 1) facilitating large-scale surveys to be carried out to collect citizens' views, and
- 2) collection of in-depth insights on policy dilemmas, e.g., the climate crisis.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Using this methodology, different governmental organisations, associations and any other type of entity will have direct, reliable and quick access to the opinions of various population groups, which are usually inaccessible to them.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Policy Insights, Whitepaper, Corpus of case study documentation, Games-based survey method, Activity designs, Open Learning Resource (educational game)

5.5.3 KER3: Datasets

Description

Collection of datasets from each case study of the project on citizens' views and insights into the climate crisis, which can provide an understanding of potential affective and behavioural change in this domain.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Access to the different datasets will allow access to big data related to the expectations of different population groups. It will facilitate analysis and decision-making in various disciplines, primarily regarding the climate crisis and environmental and sustainability issues. They can also be used in activities related to Artificial Intelligence or Data Science.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Data collection methodologies, analytic tools

Note that with datasets, the same principle from [D3.1](#) applies. This refers to data gathered during the GREAT project on climate areas and made publicly available. Portions of the data may be aggregated or individual fields removed to avoid identifying the results of individual games industry partners or the volume of their contribution to the dataset as a whole. The above will be available on the GitHub repository for ease of use, the Zenodo platform, and/or the GREAT website, depending on the most appropriate output.

5.5.4 KER4: Knowledge Corpus

Description

Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy-makers. In other words, to produce new knowledge and understand the actual and potential impact of games on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Researchers in domains related to the project (citizen science, social sciences, democracy, participatory processes) will benefit from the results obtained for future research and future projects and thus be able to advance in the creation of knowledge.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Academic papers, conference proceedings & events speeches, doctoral candidates

5.5.5 KER5: DIBL 2.0

Description

Provide a sustainable long-term commercial model where the methods and knowledge gathered in the project become available in a platform offered so policymakers, NGOs and Higher education can get the benefits as a whole package.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

It provides a real-time space for informed conversations between policy-makers and citizens.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Go-to-market for Ideal Customer Profile with offer, position and messaging for new audiences.

These should be exploited in the medium and long term, mainly after the project ends. We have already exploited some results that should be highlighted to demonstrate that exploitation occurs throughout the project's lifetime.

5.5.6 Indicators to evaluate the degree of exploitation of KERs

The GREAT project partners have defined some initial indicators to evaluate the degree of exploitation of the project results. Depending on the development of the results, the impact of the project on the stakeholders, and the advice received from the Horizon Results Booster, these indicators could be fine-tuned in deliverable D6.4. Initially, the following indicators have been identified:

Academic dimension

- # of research institutions citing project results (new academic papers, conferences)
- # of new research projects originated from the results of GREAT

Policy Dimension

- # of policy stakeholders reached by Insight Briefings
- # of policy stakeholders reached by the two project whitepapers on the use of games as a medium for education for democracy and development of skillsets in social engagement and participation, and in the use of games to obtain policy insight
- # of public institutions adopt components of the GREAT methodology

Society Dimension

- # of people using GREAT developments (e.g., 300,000 people engaged in GREAT activities)
- # of other institutions adopting components of the GREAT methodology to address future societal challenges (NGOs, multilateral organizations, associations, unions)
- # of organisations adopting GREAT methodologies and technologies in expanding co-creation and citizen science activities (NGOs, multilateral organizations, associations, unions)

Commercial Dimension

- # of games companies engaging with future GREAT programmes and activities
- # of game studios adopting GREAT toolkit for applying the GREAT method to social applications of games
- # of companies using GREAT suite of analytic methods for game activities (through licenses or other legal schemes)
- # of companies, or start-ups, applying GREAT business models
- Measure of growth and sustainability of participant companies

5.5.7 Key communication and tools to increase the degree of exploitation

Project communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities are somewhat interlinked, which can collectively improve the visibility of the project. The time and resource investments in communication and dissemination events will increase the degree to which the project results are exploited and the impact reached. In this section, we summarise several key messages that can be communicated to different

domains via different tools to increase or maximise the degree of exploitation being reached, see Table 9.

Table 9: Key communication and tools to increase the degree of exploitation

Main messages	Dimension				Communication Tool
	Commercial	Societal	Political	Academic	
GREAT provides new ways for you to provide input to policy makers and implementers.	✓	✓	✓		Embedded activities in hit games. Press releases, blog posts on the website, social media
GREAT research provides new evidence and insight on the role that games can take in society				✓	Research publications, conferences, bibliographic listings on the GREAT website and books
GREAT provides a method and data analysis resources for implementing games leveraging game data for social purposes.	✓		✓	✓	Targeted contributions to industry websites (e.g. ISFE, EDPF) and leading bloggers. For data analytics: SOLAR, LACE network
GREAT reveals new opportunities for new applications of games, with guidance, resources, demonstrators and business models.	✓				GALA, blog posts on the GREAT website. Industry conferences (e.g. Games for Good, GDC, Gamescom)
The GREAT method creates opportunities for widening participation in your activities.		✓	✓		Networking by stakeholders (e.g. with UNESCO, UNECE, EC) and policy events (European Parliament events, User Centred Policy Design, Apolitical)
The GREAT method offers new ways to consult with citizens who do not participate in traditional media and democratic process, and to assess their preferences and attitudes.		✓	✓		Social media. Press releases and newsletters.
The GREAT method is a new way to obtain feedback on results of policy implementation.			✓	✓	Events with European Institutions, national Institutions (regional and local level). Social media. Press releases and newsletters.
GREAT insight reports can help you in formulating and responding to policy on the climate crisis.		✓	✓		Press releases, blog posts on the website, social media

5.5.8 Further support for exploitation

The GREAT project results will be exploited by a series of initiatives to enhance the exploitation of research outputs and made available by the European Commission. The GREAT project has engaged directly with the Horizon Results Booster service, a service/initiative from the European Commission that provides services to EU-funded projects to help navigate the complexities of dissemination and exploitation. Horizon Booster's services encompass everything from dissemination and go-to-market strategies to advancing results towards market readiness. The service provides support to complement and supplement the GREAT exploitation strategy. Further results of Booster support will be incorporated into Deliverable D6.4, due in Month 30. Figure 7

below shows the different services provided by Horizon Results Booster in terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation.

Figure 7: Horizon Booster services (<https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>).

6. Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the GREAT project’s strategic approach to communication, dissemination, and exploitation and the mechanisms established to achieve maximum reach, impact, and longevity for the project and its outcomes. As can be seen from the methodology and ability to leverage far-reaching games, communication to a broader public audience is a key benefit of the project's communication abilities. By the end of 2024, the Play2Act case study, in collaboration with the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), has reached over 130 million gamers worldwide. The paper also outlined communication regarding how the WP6 leader, and the consortium partners disseminate outputs and results. With a collective reach of 500,000 followers on LinkedIn, the project can reach various stakeholders associated with project partners and members. The deliverable also provides clear distinctions between communication, wide dissemination of the project and its outputs, dissemination of targeted communication to those groups who may benefit directly from the work undertaken in the project and exploitation, how and by whom the project outputs will be used directly. The deliverable aims to establish the policies, procedures and processes

supporting this objective. Further activities will be informed iteratively through stakeholder feedback and the activities undertaken as the project develops over the following months. This deliverable will be updated in month 30 as D6.4 with an up-to-date view of the progress of the KPIs and a complete database of achievements across communication, dissemination and exploitation.

